

ISic4397

I.Sicily inscription 4397

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halicyae

Place of origin (modern)

Salemi

Provenance

Upper north-west panel of mosaic/basilica B, in the paleo-Christian basilica first excavated by Salinas in 1893

Coordinates

37.833019, 12.808066

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Salemi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

tessillis

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Μνήσθη

2. τι Χρίσστε Σ[απ]

3. ρικίου τοῦ δο[ύλο]

4. υ σοῦ

Apparatus

Text of Bilotta via SEG 36.829

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285072

EDR 108401

PHI 331389

Bibliography

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Troina. At 222 F18

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